

COMPUTATION OF THE DELAMINATION FORCE IN MULTILAYERED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Delamination in multilayered composite plates is studied within the scope of fracture mechanics. Using the θ -method, the energy release rate is expressed in terms of surface integrals involving both the generalized stresses and the gradient of generalized displacements. Two expressions are available. In the former, the θ -field can be continuous, but the transverse shearing force is needed. It is computed using a mixed formulation of the Kirchhoff-Love bending problem. In the latter, the θ -field must be continuously derivable. It is performed by approximating both the crack front and the θ -field by natural B3-splines. Now, a standard F.E.M. can be used. Numerical results are presented for D.C.B. specimens.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is one of the principal failure modes encountered in multilayered composite structures. For this reason, delamination has been the subject of many investigations. Most of them use a fracture mechanics approach in which the computation of the energy release rate is required.

There are several methods to compute the energy release rate. Among them, the virtual crack closure technique (VCCT [1], [2]) is certainly the most widely used. This method has two drawbacks : (i) it is costly to run because it requires a very refined mesh near the crack front [3], and (ii) it does not give access to the second derivative of the mechanical energy which is needed to study the crack propagation stability.

In this paper, we use the so-called θ -method in which the mechanical energy is derived analytically with respect to a virtual displacement of the crack front, say θ [4], [5]. Two expressions of the energy release rate are available, depending on the retained degree of derivation of the θ field. They are discussed and, for each case, the approximation of both the θ field and the plate problem is presented. Finally, numerical results are compared to those obtained by Davidson on D.C.B. specimens [3].

EXPRESSION OF THE ENERGY RELEASE RATE

Let us consider a D.C.B. specimen that fills the domain Ω of the space as depicted on figure 1, exhibiting a delamination located at an interface parallel to the mid-plane ω of the plate. Let us assume that the delamination propagates at the interface ; then, the propagation can be described by a vector field $\theta = (\theta_1(x_1, x_2), \theta_2(x_1, x_2), 0)$ where the components θ_α (greek indices take the values 1 and 2) are regular functions with support restricted to a neighbourhood of the crack front γ_f . For any $\eta > 0$, we associate to θ the mapping F^η defined by :

$$F^\eta: \Omega \rightarrow \Omega^\eta; x \rightarrow x^\eta = x + \eta\theta(x)$$

Figure 1. Domain definition and notations.

If J^η and J are the mechanical energy of the Kirchhoff-Love plate model defined on Ω^η and Ω respectively, then the energy release rate associated to the displacement θ of the crack front is defined as the limit :

$$g(\theta) = - \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0} \frac{J^\eta - J}{\eta}$$

It is expressed as [5] :

$$\begin{aligned}
 g(\theta) = & -\frac{1}{2} \int_{\omega} n_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial \mu_\beta}{\partial x_\alpha} \operatorname{div} \theta + \int_{\omega} n_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial \mu_\beta}{\partial x_\lambda} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta_\lambda}{\partial x_\alpha} \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\omega} m_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial \mu_\beta}{\partial x_\alpha} \operatorname{div} \theta - \int_{\omega} m_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial \mu_\beta}{\partial x_\lambda} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta_\lambda}{\partial x_\alpha} \\
 & - \int_{\omega} m_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\mu_\lambda \frac{\partial \theta_\lambda}{\partial x_\alpha} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where n and m are the membrane and bending stresses defined as :

$$(n_{\alpha\beta}, m_{\alpha\beta}) = \int_{h^-}^{h^+} (1, x_3) \sigma_{\alpha\beta} dx_3$$

and u and μ are the displacement and the rotation vectors respectively ($\mu = \nabla u_3$).

One can retain Eqn (1). Then the last integral involves second order derivatives of θ . As a consequence, θ must be defined by continuously derivable functions. An alternative is to integrate by parts this integral. One obtains :

$$\int_{\omega} m_{\alpha\beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{\beta}} \left(\mu_{\lambda} \frac{\partial \theta_{\lambda}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} \right) = - \int_{\omega} q_{\alpha} \mu_{\lambda} \frac{\partial \theta_{\lambda}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} \quad (2)$$

$$+ \int_{\gamma_f} v_{\beta} [m_{\alpha\beta}] \mu_{\lambda} \frac{\partial \theta_{\lambda}}{\partial x_{\alpha}} + \int_{\gamma_f} v_{\beta} m_{\alpha\beta} \mu_{\lambda} \frac{\partial \theta_{\lambda}}{\partial x_{\alpha}}$$

Now, θ can be defined using continuous functions only, but the computation of the transverse shearing force

$$q_{\alpha} = \frac{\partial m_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial x_{\beta}}$$

is now required.

Finally, a further integration by parts allows us to put the energy release rate in the form :

$$g(\theta) = \int_{\gamma_f} G \theta \cdot v \quad (3)$$

G is the delamination force defined along the crack front.

NUMERICAL APPROXIMATION

APPROXIMATION ASSOCIATED TO EQN (1)

First of all, we focus our attention to the approximation of γ_f and θ . The crack front is defined by geometric nodes and by its tangents at the edges. Then γ_f is approximated using natural B3-splines. The components θ_{α} are interpolated from nodal values defined at the geometric nodes using natural B3-splines along γ_f and bell-shaped cubic polynomials in the x_1 direction.

The plate is viewed as an assembly of three subplates connected along γ_f where the continuity of both the displacements and the rotations are insured. Each subplate is modelled using a Mindlin plate model and a finite element approximation is made using eight-noded quadrilateral elements.

APPROXIMATION ASSOCIATED TO EQN (2)

Here, the main difficulty consists in obtaining accurate values for the transverse shearing force q . To this hand, a mixed formulation of the Kirchoff-Love bending problem is retained. It is based upon the following decomposition of q [6] :

$$q = \nabla\phi + \nabla_x\psi$$

The unknowns of the problem are the displacement u , the rotation μ and the functions ϕ and ψ . They are approximated using triangular elements with : (i) linear shape functions for u_3 , ϕ and ψ , and (ii) linear plus bubble shape functions for u_α and μ .

With Eqn (2), θ can be simply continuous. It is defined on elements having at least one node located on γ_f and interpolated by linear shape functions. Of course, θ can also be defined as in the previous case.

COMPUTATION OF THE DELAMINATION FORCE

The finite element approximation of Eqn (1) or Eqn (2) takes the form

$$g(\theta) = \{\theta\}^t \cdot \{g\} \quad (4)$$

where $\{\theta\}$ is the vector of the θ nodal values defined at the nodes located on γ_f only, and $\{g\}$ can be viewed as a generalized delamination force. To go back to the nodal values $\{G\}$ of the delamination force, it is assumed that Eqn (3) is computed by approximating G with suitable shape functions. The more convenient choice is to take the same approximation for both θ and G . Then, Eqn (3) can be written as

$$g(\theta) = \{\theta\}^t \cdot [M] \cdot \{G\} \quad (5)$$

where $[M]$ is a symmetric definite positive matrix. Finally, by Eqn (4) and Eqn (5), we find that $\{G\}$ is obtained by solving the following linear system :

$$[M] \cdot \{G\} = \{g\}$$

NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS

The numerical experiments concern the D.C.B. specimens previously studied by Davidson [3]. The specimen width is discretized by 16 elements whereas each delaminated leg is discretized by 19 and 13 rows of elements in the Mindlin and in the mixed model cases respectively. The B3-splines approximation of both θ and γ_f is made using 5 geometric nodes. The normalized values of G along γ_f are reported in Fig. 2 in the case of a straight crack front and for an aspect ratio $a/b=1$. This is the most severe case for the Kirchhoff-Love plate model as the thickness ratio is greater than $1/15$. The obtained results are in good agreement with the Davidson's results, especially those given by the mixed model. For the $\pm 15^\circ$ angle-ply specimen, the stress singularities exhibited by the Mindlin plate model at the crack front edges reduces the accuracy. It is a serious advantage of the Kirchhoff-Love plate model to remove this singular behaviour.

Figure 2. Repartition of the normalized delamination force along the crack front for a D.C.B. specimen with an aspect ratio = 1.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. The curved crack front case - isotropic material aspect ratio = 1.

(a) Finite element mesh

(b) Normalized delamination force along the crack front.

Fig. 3 shows the repartition of G obtained in the case of a curved crack front for a specimen made of isotropic material.

CONCLUSION

We have just explained a method for computing the energy release rate that appears accurate, even used with relatively coarse meshes. The B3-splines approximation allows to use standard displacements F.E.M. and has a smoothing effect on the results. Due to the stress singularities exhibited by the Mindlin plate model, it is better to use the Kirchhoff-Love plate model, even in the case of thick plates.

Finally, it is pointed out that the θ -method allows to derive the expression of the second derivative of the mechanical energy making possible the study of the delamination propagation stability [7].

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